

Birth year	Names	First paper	PhD ступінь	Retired	Sex	Characteristics	Life years
1860	Mrs. Lewis Milne	1910		1932 w		British English anthropologist	1860-1932
1860	Ignác Kúnos	1882	1882	1945		Hungarian linguist, turkologist, folklorist	1860-1945
1860	Karl Wessely	1882	1985	1922		Austrian palaeographer and papyrus scholar	1860-1931
1860	Renward Brandstetter	1883	1883	1927		Swiss philologist and linguist who published about medieval and modern Swiss dialects language and the older Swiss theatre history and studied the insular Malayo-Polynesian languages	1860-1942
1860	Johannes Ilberg	1883	1883	1924		German educator and classical philologist who was the author of numerous works on ancient Greek medicine	1860-1930
1860	Otto Jespersen	1885	1891	1925		Danish linguist	1860-1943
1860	Alfred Gercke	1885	1885	1921		German classical philologist	1860-1922
1860	George Oliver Curme	1887	1888	1939		American grammarian and philologist	1860-1948
1860	George Lyman Kittredge	1887		1936		American professor of English literature	1860-1941
1860	Gustav Weigand	1888	1888	1930		German linguist and specialist in Balkan languages, especially Romanian and Aromanian	1860-1930
1860	Milan Rešetar	1889	1889	1928		Serbian linguist, historian and literary critic	1860-1942
1860	Emma Elizabeth Thoyts	1889		1910 w		British English palaeographer, historian and genealogist	1860-1949
1860	Telesforo de Aranzadi	1889		1931		Spanish Basque scientist, specialist in anthropology, botany and zoology	1860-1945
1860	Walter Baldwin Spencer	1890	No	1919		British English-Australian biologist and anthropologist	1860-1929
1860	Frank Frost Abbott	1891	1891	1912		American classical scholar	1860-1924
1860	Ferdinand Brunot	1891	1891	1928		French linguist and philologist	1860-1938
1860	Théodore Reinach	1891		1928		French archaeologist, mathematician, lawyer, papyrologist, philologist, epigrapher, historian, numismatist, musicologist, professor, and politician	1860-1928
1860	Robert Steele	1893		1941		British scholar, medievalist	1860-1944
1860	Patrick Stephen Dinneen	1904		1934		Irish lexicographer and historian, and a leading figure in the Gaelic revival	1860-1934
1861	Wilhelm Meyer-Lübke	1883	1883	1936		Swiss philologist of the Neogrammarian school of linguistics	1861-1936
1861	Morris Jastrow Jr.	1884	1884	1921		Polish-American orientalist and librarian associated	1861-1921

1861	Maurice Prou	1884		1930	French archivist, paleographer and numismatist	1861-1930
1861	Georg Steindorff	1884	1884	1934	German Egyptologist	1861-1951
1861	James Mooney	1885	No	1921	American ethnographer who lived for several years among the Cherokee	1861-1921
1861	Carl Ferdinand Friedrich Lehmann-Haupt	1886	1886	1935	German orientalist and historian	1861-1938
1861	Walter Roth	1886	No	1928	British colonial administrator, anthropologist and medical practitioner	1861-1933
1861	Matija Murko	1886	1886	1931	Slovenian scholar, known mostly for his work on oral epic traditions in Serbian, Bosnian and Croatian	1861-1952
1861	Maurice Wilmotte	1886		1931	Belgian philologist	1861-1942
1861	E. J. Rapson	1887		1936	British numismatist, philologist and professor of Sanskrit at the University of Cambridge	1861-1937
1861	Peter Jensen	1890	1890	1928	German orientalist and proponent of the Christ myth theory	1861-1936
1861	Pezavia O'Connell	1898	1898	1930	American Methodist minister, scholar of Hebrew, and African-American activist	1861-1930
1861	William Edward Soothill	1899		1935	British Methodist missionary to China who later became Professor of Chinese at University College, Oxford, and a leading British sinologist	1861-1935
1862	William Peterfield Trent	1884	1884	1929	American academic and the author/editor of many books	1862-1939
1862	Theodor Siebs	1885	1885	1929	German linguist	1862-1941
1862	Heinrich Zimmern	1885	1885	1929	German Assyriologist	1862-1931
1862	Franz Xaver Kugler	1885	1885	1929	German chemist, mathematician, Assyriologist, and Jesuit priest	1862-1929
1862	Sima Trojanović	1885	1885	1921	Serbian ethnologist and the first university-trained anthropologist	1862-1935
1862	Josef Strzygowski	1885	1885	1933	Polish-Austrian art historian known for his theories promoting influences from the art of the Near East on European art	1862-1941
1862	Fyodor Braun	1885	1885	1932	Russian-German scholar who provided philological and mythological backing for the Normanist theory	1862-1942
1862	A. V. Williams Jackson	1886	1886	1935	American specialist on Indo-European languages	1862-1937

1862	Émile Mâle	1886	1886	1937	French art historian, one of the first to study medieval, mostly sacral French art and the influence of Eastern European iconography thereon	1862-1954
1862	Leo Wiener	1887		1930	Russian-American historian, linguist, author and translator	1862-1939
1862	Thomas William Allen	1887		1950	British English classicist, scholar of Ancient Greek and palaeographer	1862-1950
1862	Rudolf Much	1887	1887	1934	Austrian Germanist, considered one of the founding fathers of Germanic studies	1862-1936
1862	Charles Hall Grandgent	1887		1923	American romance philologist and Italian scholar	1862-1939
1862	Alfred Gudeman	1888	1888	1935	American-German classical scholar	1862-1942
1862	Philipp August Becker	1888	1888	1947	German Romanist	1862-1947
1862	Hermann Gunkel	1888		1927	German Old Testament scholar, founded form criticism	1862-1932
1862	Hermann Georg Fiedler	1888	1888	1937	German the Taylor Professor of the German Language and Literature	1862-1945
1862	Albert Ehrhard	1888	1888	1927	German Catholic theologian, church historian and Byzantinist	1862-1940
1862	Edward Granville Browne	1889		1912	British orientalist (numerous articles and books, mainly in the areas of history and literature)	1862-1926
1862	Edward Porębowicz	1890	1890	1926	Polish romanist, poet, translator, literary researcher	1862-1937
1862	James Taft Hatfield	1890	1890	1934	American philologist	1862-1945
1862	Georg Jacob	1892	1892	1932	German scholar of Islamic studies and an Orientalist founder of Turkology as a modern academic discipline in Germany	1862-1937
1862	Wilhelm Max Müller	1893		1919	American orientalist	1862-1919
1862	Carl Vilhelm Hartman	1894	No	1923	Swedish botanist and anthropologist	1862-1941
1862	Anton Mitov	1896		1927	Bulgarian painter, art critic, art historian, social activist and corresponding member of the Bulgarian Academy of Sciences	1862-1930
1862	Esther Boise Van Deman	1898	1898	1930 w	American leading archaeologist (Roman archaeology)	1862-1937
1862	Benno Jacob	1899	1899	1929	German liberal rabbi and Bible scholar	1862-1945
1863	Cyrus Adler	1883	1883	1940	American educator, Jewish religious leader and scholar	1863-1940
1863	Alexander Harkavy	1885	No	1939	Belarusian-American writer, lexicographer and linguist.	1863-1939

1863	Sergey Oldenburg	1885	1885	1929	Russian orientalist who specialized in Buddhist studies	1863-1934
1863	Hermann Klaatsch	1885	1885	1916	German physician, anatomist, physical anthropologist, evolutionist, and professor	1863-1916
1863	Félix Regnault	1885		1928	French physician, anthropologist and prehistorian	1863-1938
1863	Karl Friedrich Heinrich Bruchmann	1885	1885	1919	German classical philologist	1863-1919
1863	Georges Dottin	1886	1896	1927	French philologist, professor for Greek language and literature at the University of Rennes	1863-1928
1863	Abel Lefranc	1886	1886	1952	French historian of French literature, expert on Rabelais, and the principal advocate of the Derbyite theory of Shakespeare authorship	1863-1952
1863	Albert Bachmann	1886	1886	1934	Swiss lexicographer and dialectologist, professor for Germanic philology	1863-1934
1863	Georg Witkowski	1886	1886	1933	German literary historian	1863-1939
1863	Wilhelm Schulze	1887	1887	1932	German Linguist, Indo-Europeanist and classical philologist	1863-1935
1863	Alfredo Panzini	1887	1887	1939	Italian novelist and lexicographer	1863-1939
1863	Otto Kern	1888	1888	1931	German classical philologist, archaeologist and epigraphist	1863-1942
1863	Duncan Black MacDonald	1888		1925	American orientalist	1863-1943
1863	August Brinkmann	1888	1888	1920	German classicist and philologist	1863-1923
1863	Gustav Rolin	1888	1888	1933	Austrian Romanist	1863-1937
1863	Lyubomir Miletich	1889	1889	1937	Bulgarian linguist, ethnographer, dialectologist and historian, chairman of the Bulgarian Academy of Sciences	1863-1937
1863	Adolph Goldschmidt	1889	1889	1929	German Jewish art historian	1863-1944
1863	Sylvain Lévi	1890	1890	1935	French influential orientalist and indologist who taught Sanskrit and Indian religion at the École pratique des hautes études	1863-1935
1863	Frederic G. Kenyon	1891		1931	British palaeographer and biblical and classical scholar	1863-1952
1863	Raymond Weeks	1892	1897	1929	American linguist and academic	1863-1954
1863	Frederick Klaeber	1892	1892	1931	German Professor of Old and Middle English	1863-1954
1863	Charles Cutler Torrey	1892	1892	1936	American historian, archaeologist and scholar	1863-1956

1863	Siegfried Sudhaus	1892	1892	1914	German classical philologist and papyrologist	1863-1914
1863	Johannes Weiß	1892		1914	German Protestant theologian and biblical exegete	1863-1914
1863	Edward Albert Gait	1893	No	1920	British administrator in the Indian Civil Service	1863-1950
1863	Frederick Gymer Parsons	1894	No	1929	British writer and scientist, specialising in the fields of anatomy and anthropology	1863-1943
1863	Ernst Sieper	1895	1895	1916	German Anglist	1863-1916
1863	Margaret Murray	1895	No	1935	w British (Anglo-Indian) Egyptologist, archaeologist, anthropologist, historian, and folklorist	1863-1963
1863	Mary Durham	1899	No	1944	w British artist, anthropologist, noted Albanophile and writer who became famous for her anthropological accounts of life in Albania in the early 20th century	1863-1944
1863	George Grant MacCurdy	1900	1905	1945	American anthropologist	1863-1947
1863	Antoine Cabaton	1901		1933	French philologist, one of the founders of the insulindian studies	1863-1942
1864	Paul Boyer	1886	1886	1936	French slavist, administrator	1864-1949
1864	Alfred Jeremias	1886	1886	1935	German pastor, Assyriologist and an expert on the religions of the Ancient Near East	1864-1935
1864	Paul Wendland	1886		1915	German classical philologist	1864-1915
1864	Heinrich Wölfflin	1886	1886	1934	Swiss art historian, whose objective classifying principles ("painterly" vs. "linear" and the like) were influential in the development of formal analysis in art history in the early 20th century	1864-1945
1864	Paul Wendland	1886	1886	1915	German classical philologist	1864-1915
1864	Robert Seymour Conway	1888		1929	British classical scholar and comparative philologist	1864-1933
1864	August Conrady	1888		1925	German sinologist and linguist	1864-1925
1864	Wilhelm Streitberg	1888	1888	1925	German Indo-Europeanist, specializing in Germanic languages	1864-1925
1864	W. H. R. Rivers	1888		1922	British English anthropologist, neurologist, ethnologist and psychiatrist, best known for his work treating First World War officers who were suffering from shell shock	1864-1922
1864	Auguste Audollent	1890		1937	French historian, archaeologist and Latin epigrapher, specialist of ancient Rome	1864-1943
1864	Alexey Kharuzin	1890		1927	Russian ethnographer, anthropologist, and statesman	1864-1932

1864	Joseph Bédier	1890		1938	French writer and scholar and historian of medieval France	1864-1938
1864	Alexander Khakhanov	1890		1912	Georgian-Russian historian, archaeologist, and one of the most acclaimed scholars of Georgian literature	1864-1912
1864	Karl Weule	1891	1891	1926	German geographer and ethnologist	1864-1926
1864	Ioan Bogdan	1891		1919	Romanian historian and philologist	1864-1919
1864	Josef Markwart	1892	1892	1930	German historian and orientalist	1864-1930
1864	C. Alphonso Smith	1893	1893	1924	American Professor of English, college dean, philologist, and folklorist (writer known as O. Henry)	1864-1924
1864	Gabriel Ferrand	1893	1909	1935	French orientalist specialised on the Madagascar	1864-1935
1864	Mabel Haynes Bode	1893		1918 w	British one of the first women to enter the academic fields of Pali, Sanskrit and Buddhist studies	1864-1922
1864	Oskar Franz Walzel	1894	1894	1933	Austrian-German Literary scholar	1864-1944
1864	Clarence G. Child	1895	1895	1938	American educator, scholar of medieval literature, and hobbyist mathematician who served as dean of the graduate school	1864-1948
1864	Thomas Walker Arnold	1896		1930	British orientalist and historian of Islamic art	1864-1930
1864	James Teit	1898	No	1922	Canadian anthropologist, photographer and guide who worked with Franz Boas to study Interior Salish First Nations peoples in the late 19th and early 20th centuries	1864-1922
1864	Edward Dwelly	1901		1939	British English lexicographer and genealogist	1864-1939